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A REVIEW OF ADULTERATION IN HERBAL MEDICINE WITH DIFFERENT CLASS ALLOPATHIC DRUGS

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ABSTRACT

Herbal Formulations are highly popular worldwide because of the less side effect of the herbal formulation. Based on current research show that undeclared synthetic chemical constituents were found in the Therapeutic herbal medicines. Hence the quality of the herbal medicine are more concern by the world consumers and regulators. Intentionally or non-Intentionally some of the herbal medicine were contaminated by the microbial contamination, excessive or banned pesticide, heavy metal and chemical toxin with all possible problem. Adulteration of Herbal Medicinal Products with synthetic drug are producing major health risk and major concern to the drug regulatory agency. Some of the herbal supplements are adulterated with some unlabeled chemical constituents. Due to this take precaution against adulterated herbal medicines are necessary. In this review shown that there was many herbal medicines adulterated with chemical constituents and that was identified by different analytical techniques.

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INTRODUCTION

Adulteration in herbal products:

Herbal Formulations are highly popular worldwide because of the less side effect of the herbal formulation. Based on current research show that undeclared synthetic chemical constituents were found in the THMs (Therapeutic herbal medicines). Hence the quality of the herbal medicine are more concern by the world consumers and regulators. The quality of the herbal medicine are mainly controlled by the regulatory requirements. With this concern regulatory standard and their efficacy, Safety, legislation, quality. ⁽¹⁾

Intentionally or non-Intentionally some of the herbal medicine were contaminated by the microbial contamination, excessive or banned pesticide, heavy metal and chemical toxin with all possible problem. Hence herbal formulation are reviewed for longer period of time, and other important safety issue have not considered. Beside the toxicity some of the conventional drugs are also possible adulterations. Adulteration of herbal formulation was mainly found in following categories of drug like Cortisone and its derivatives, anti-allergic substances, oral anti-diabetic agents and life style medicines as anorexic drugs and anti-impotency drugs. Hence this is one of the concern which may not be neglected. ⁽²⁾

Miller et al has defined that “the addition of an impure or inferior component not ordinarily part of that substance or removal of a crucial entity usually used to imply that a substance is debased (desecrated) as a result”. When the necessary natural substances are in shortage or expensive or to increase the pharmacological effect adulteration are internationally doen. Recently Herbal medicine are reported to contain some undeclared chemical constituents. ⁽³⁾

Adulteration of HMPs with synthetic drug are producing major health risk and major concern to the drug regulatory agency. Some of the herbal supplements are adulterated with some unlabeled chemical constituents. ⁽⁴⁾

For example: Sildenafil (Viagra) were found to be present in the some sexual performance enhancing herbal formulations. ⁽¹²⁾ Herbal formulation adulteration have screen for the herbal supplements in one LC-MS run. During 1990-2015 herbal formulation have been reviewed for their toxicity and analyzed by various analytical techniques. Different search engine like Google Scholar, PubMed, SciFinder and FDA databases were used with search word herbal medicine, traditional medicine, traditional, Chinese medicine. Some of the herbal formulation were found to contain some internationally added undeclared chemical constituents. ⁽⁴⁾

WHO guideline for herbal medicine⁽²⁾

This WHO guidelines present general consideration on potentially hazardous contaminants and residue in herbal medicines and include guiding principle of assessing quality of herbal medicines in terms of major contaminants and residues. It also recommends analytical method for qualitative and quantitative determination of such contaminants and residue.

Relating contaminants and residues in herbal medicines

In general the contaminants and residues in herbal medicines have been adopted verbatim or where necessary adapted from the definitions for pesticide residue in foods, developed by the Codex Alimentarius Commissio and the joint FAO/WHO meeting on pesticide residue.

Herbal Medicine in US⁽⁵⁾

Nearly 1 in 5 adults in the United States report taking an herbal product. 1 written records of the use of herbal medicine date back more than 5,000 years. 2 In fact, for most of history, herbal medicine was the only medicine. Even as recently as 1890, 59% of the listings in the US Pharmacopeia were from herbal products, 3 and it has been estimated that as many as one third to one half of currently used drugs were originally derived from plants.

An herb can be any form of a plant or plant product, including leaves, stems, flowers, roots, and seeds. These plants can either be sold raw or as extracts, where the plant is macerated with water, alcohol, or other solvents to extract some of the chemicals. The resulting products contain dozens of chemicals, including fatty acids, sterols, alkaloids, flavonoids, glycosides, saponins, and others. 5 Because any given herb contains multiple ingredients, some manufacturers attempt to create standardized herbal products by identifying a suspected active ingredient and altering the manufacturing process to obtain a consistent amount of this chemical. For most herbs, the exact chemical, or combination of chemicals, that produce a biological effect is unknown, and it is therefore difficult (if not impossible) to create a precise “chemical fingerprint” of the optimum herbal product.

Factors affecting quality & purity of Herbal Medicines⁽⁶⁾

Drug adulteration

Adulteration may be defined as mixing or substituting the original drug material with other spurious, inferior, defective, spoiled, useless other parts of same or different plant or harmful substances or drug which do not confirm with the official standards.

Adulteration may takes place by two ways:

- Direct or intentional adulteration
- Indirect or unintentional adulteration

Examples for Adulteration,

A. With artificially manufactured materials, e.g. nutmeg is adulterated with basswood prepared to the required shape and size, the colored paraffin wax is used in place of beeswax.

B. With inferior quality materials, e.g. Belladonna leaves are substituted with Ailanthus leaves, papaya seeds to adulterate Piper nigrum.

C. With harmful / fictitious substances drugs, e.g. Pieces of amber colored glass in colophony, limestone in asafetida, lead shot in opium, white oil in coconut oil, cocoa butter with stearin or paraffin.

D. Adulteration of powders, e.g. powder liquorice or gentian admixed with powder olive stones, under the name of cinchona.

Faulty collection

Imperfect preparation

Non removal of associated structures e.g. stems are collected with leaves, flowers, fruits. Non-removal of undesirable parts or structures e.g. cork should be removed from ginger rhizome. Proper drying conditions should be adhered. Improper drying may lead to unintentional adulteration e.g. if digitalis leaves are dried above 65 °C decomposition of glycosides by enzymatic hydrolysis.

Incorrect storage

Deterioration happens especially during storage, leading to the loss of the active ingredients, production of metabolites with no activity and, in extreme cases, the production of toxic metabolites. Physical factors such as air (oxygen), humidity, light, and temperature can bring about deterioration directly or indirectly.

Gross substitution with plant material

Substitution with exhausted drugs

Chemical Adulteration in herbal medicinal products⁽⁷⁾

Many herbal medicinal products have been found to contain synthetic prescription drugs as chemical adulterants. This has become evident by the number of toxicity cases and adverse reactions reported in which casualties were reported via analytical techniques that detected the presence of chemical adulterants in them, which could be responsible for their toxicity. The adulteration of herbal medicinal products with synthetic drugs continues to be a serious problem for regulatory agencies. This review provides up to date information on cases of toxicity, major chemical adulterants in herbal medicinal products, and current analytical techniques used for their detection.

Table Comparison of Analytical Techniques.

Techniques	Advantages	Disadvantages
LC-MS & HPLC	Analyzes most compounds	ESI is difficult to contribute to spectral databases based on available standards in different labs
GC & GC-MS	High resolution and sensitivity, good accuracy, rapid	Only separates volatile compounds
¹ H NMR	Detects specific structural components	Expensive, time-consuming
CE & CE-MS	Small amounts of sample and solvent have high separation efficiency, short analysis, time, inexpensive	Improvements can be made with accuracy
TLC & HPTLC	Simple, rapid, inexpensive can use several different solvents	Short stationary phase, high detection limit, can be affected by humidity and temperature

Analysis of Adulterated Herbal Medicines and dietary supplements marketed for weight loss by ¹H NMR⁽⁸⁾

Twenty herbal medicines or dietary supplements marketed as natural slimming products were analyzed by Diffusion Ordered Spectroscopy (DOSY) 1H NMR and DOSY-COSY 1H NMR. The method allows analysis of the whole sample with detection of both active and inactive ingredients in these complex matrices. Among the 20 formulations analyzed, 2 were strictly herbal and 4 had a composition corresponding to declared ingredients on the packaging or the leaflet. The others were all adulterated. Eight formulations contain sibutramine alone at doses ranging from 4.4 to 30.5 mg/capsule. Five formulations contain sibutramine (from 5.0 to 19.6 mg/capsule or tablet) in combination with phenolphthalein (from 4.4 to 66.1 mg/capsule), and the last formulation was adulterated with synephrine (19.5 mg/capsule). Quantification of the actives was carried out with 1H NMR. Several other compounds were also characterized including methylsynephrine, vitaberin, sugars, vitamins etc. DOSY NMR is thus proposed as a useful tool for detection of unexpected adulteration.

Detection of *Actaea racemosa* Adulteration⁽⁹⁾

Actaea racemosa L. (black cohosh; syn. *Cimicifuga racemosa* L. Nutt.) is a native North American perennial whose root and rhizome preparations are commercially available as phyto medicines and dietary supplements, primarily for management of menopausal symptoms. Despite its wide use, methods that accurately identify processed *A. racemosa* are not well established; product adulteration remains a concern. Because of its similar appearance and growing locales, *A. racemosa* has been unintentionally mixed with other species of the genus, such as *Actaea pachypoda* Eil. (White cohosh) and more commonly *Actaea podocarpa* DC. (Yellow cohosh). The genus *Actaea* also has 23 temperate species with numerous common names, which can also contribute to the misidentification of plant material. Consequently, a variety of *Actaea* spp. are common adulterants of commercially available black cohosh preparations. Thin-layer chromatography (TLC) and combined TLC-bioluminescence (Bioluminex™) are efficient, economical, and effective techniques which provide characteristic patterns and toxicity profiles for each plant species.

These data indicate that common black cohosh adulterants, such as yellow cohosh, can be differentiated from black cohosh by TLC and TLC-bioluminescence. This study also showed that unknown contaminants that were not detected using standard *A. racemosa* identity techniques were readily detected by TLC and TLC-bioluminescence.

Adulteration in Slimming product⁽¹⁰⁾

To review pharmaceutical analogue adulteration of nonprescription slimming products. For this Retrospective study choose for design. All patients known to have been hospitalized after taking slimming products adulterated with pharmaceutical analogues from September 2004 to December 2006. Main outcome measures age, reasons for hospital admission, major biochemical findings, and toxicology analysis results of the offending slimming products.

N-nitrosofenfluramine, an analogue of fenfluramine with hepatotoxic effect, was found in two slimming products. Three patients were hospitalized after taking these slimming products, one of whom developed liver failure treated by liver transplantation. Another slimming product was found to contain N-desmethyl-sibutramine, an analogue of sibutramine. A patient with an unremarkable medical history developed acute psychosis after taking the latter product for 1 week.

Screening of Indian aphrodisiac ayurvedic/herbal healthcare products for adulteration using LC/PDA and extracted ion LC-MS/TOF⁽¹¹⁾

Ayurvedic/herbal healthcare products are considered safe under the impression that they are derived from natural products. But recently, there have been several reports worldwide on the adulteration of synthetic PDE-5 inhibitors in aphrodisiac herbal formulations. Therefore, the objective of the present study was to explore the presence of synthetic PDE-5 inhibitors (sildenafil, tadalafil and/or vardenafil) in ayurvedic/herbal healthcare products sold in Indian market for aphrodisiac/related uses. In total, 85 herbal formulations (HFs) were included in the study. The formulations were extracted with methanol and subjected to centrifugation. The supernatant was analysed by HPLC and LC-MS/TOF. Early detection of the presence of sildenafil, tadalafil and vardenafil in the herbal samples was done by the study of extracted ion mass chromatograms at their *m/z* values of respective parent ions, and two prominent fragments of each. In case of sildenafil and tadalafil, adulteration was also detected by comparing the relative retention times (RRT) and UV spectra. Further substantiation was done through comparison of accurate mass spectra with those of the two available standards. Of the 85 HFs tested, only one was eventually found to be adulterated with sildenafil. The extent of adulterant in this sample was determined to be the therapeutic dose in the formulation. The study thus indicates emergence of the problem of adulteration of Indian herbal products with PDE-5 inhibitors.

Adulteration in herbal Anti-diabetic formulations:

Due to the disease like diabetes multiple body system may be damaged. Diabetes were affected by the 220 million people worldwide. Among the all 90 % population was observed type II (non-insulin-dependent) diabetes (World Health Organization, 2009). Sulfonylureas, Thiazolidinedione, Meglitinides, Biguanides and α -Glucosidase inhibitors are the major classes of the synthetic drug. During such periods of time dietary supplements and Chinese Proprietary Medicines (CPMs) were increase popularity among the patients. To get the dual advantage some of the manufacturer illegally add synthetic anti-diabetic drugs in their products. Hence CPMs and dietary supplements have to be analyzed for the existence of illegal fake drugs⁽¹²⁻¹³⁾.

CONCLUSIONS

Some herbal medicinal products have been reported to cause severe adverse reactions due to their adulteration. PDE-5is, sibutramine, and fenfluramine are common examples of adulterants found in HMPs that have led people to be hospitalized. With LC- MS and combined methods, it is becoming easier to detect adulterants and confirm their presence. In slimming product analogues, created by modifying the chemical structures of pharmaceuticals, are used as adulterants in non-prescription slimming products, in an attempt to evade regulatory inspection. The imperceptible use of these analogues is very dangerous because they have not been tested formally for efficacy and safety. In view of the potential harm to the public, more effective and proactive measures are required to guard against the illicit use of pharmaceutical analogues. There is also a need for increased awareness among the public and the medical professionals about this emerging threat. In other study was carried out to explore Indian aphrodisiac herbal formulations for adulteration with PDE-5 inhibitor drugs. The LC-PDA and LC-MS based strategy was employed for the purpose. Of the total of 85 Indian aphrodisiac herbal formulations included in the study, only onewas found to contain sildenafil. This shows initiation of the clandestine activity, though limited yet.

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